

Women's Independence as a Source from Within

Dr. M. Rajeshwari, Lecturer in English, SVVN PU and Degree College, Neraluru, Bangalore.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15245571

Abstract

This article traces the empowerment of women through self-study and inner independence. It argues that right empowerment comes from internal strength and explains the substantiation of social change. The paper highlights that self-reliance and self-appraisal play key roles in a woman's quest to achieve independence. By studying the life story of the renowned British author J.K. Rowling and in comparison to the lead women characters of the Tamil film "Magalir Mattum" (2017), the article explores the complex nature of women's empowerment. The paper studies Rowling's legacy from personal and financial hardships to reaching a literary reputation as an example of self-assurance. Her life is followed by despair, a failed marriage and the challenges of single motherhood. Rowling empowers her with writing and channels her sorrow into innovative expression. Similarly, the film "Magalir Mattum" depicts the aspirations of three women who have been subdued by marriage and social prospects. As they embark on reconnection and self-discovery in their life, the characters reclaim their identities and autonomy towards empowerment. The movie tackles the troubles endured by women including gender discrimination, social stress and the suppression of oppression of women in terms of marriage. Both illustrate that empowerment is not always something bestowed but a substitute that evolved from inside and requires courage to break off the imposed constraints that hinder their lives. The article concludes by affirming that women's independence is founded on self-reliance and internal affirmation. It can be achieved by the pursuit of one's passions, dreams and self-reliance. This paper opens up a sound argument on the need for self-reliance in real and fictional women to accomplish empowerment and independence.

Keywords: J. K. Rowling, *Magalir Mattum*, Self-determination, Comparative Study.

Introduction

Women's empowerment is all about attaining independence from within. Independence is not something that one can get from the outer world. The article is going to put forth the idea that independence is an individual realization and an attempt to come out of the shell. It is the chance to think about what we cannot do and to we can do. Women are said to be untapped and underappreciated for their talents and capacity. The article is going to explore the view that women should have the means to support themselves. The freedom should only be acquired by herself and not be expected from the external world. She is the one who should appreciate herself as a more beautiful, happier and stronger woman. Women's independence can be achieved only if they learn to follow their willpower and intellect. The article uses the life of J.K. Rowling as a real-life exemplification and uses the movie *Magalir Mattum* as a fictional example to explore the view that women's independence is self-determination and the realization of self-sufficiency.

Independence as a Source from Within

The article is going to portray the life journey of J.K. Rowling. She has stated herself as the biggest failure. Now, J.K. Rowling is an author whose book series has been translated

into 73 languages and sold millions of copies. Her life was not an easy one. Her achievements were not acquired without grievances. Her dream of writing a book was pulled away by the devastating death of her mother. Pugh points out,

Rowling's literary fiction *The Casual Vacancy* and her detective series featuring Cormoran Strike, written under the pseudonym Robert Galbraith. Through this comprehensive overview of Rowling's body of work, Pugh reveals the vast web of connections between yesteryear's stories and Rowling's vivid creations. (Tison Pugh, *Book Info, JSTOR*)

Rowling ceased working on the book and sank into depression. In the hope of digging herself out of depression, she took a job as an English teacher. The dream of writing a book did not go as planned. Even more to her grievance, she ended up with a failed marriage and she had to raise alone her baby daughter. On the website of J.K. Rowling, one can see;

The young Jo grew up surrounded by books. "I lived for books," she has said. "I was your basic common-or-garden bookworm, complete with freckles and National Health spectacles." (jkrowling.com)

It was none but herself who found consolation in writing. Rowling found freedom and real happiness in doing what she loved. It was only her inner guts which placed her in the position she had once feared most. Independence and happiness to her were moving away from her inessentials. Her self-realization and her inner energy directed her dreams on a progressive path. The attitude of strengthening herself against rejections and depression moved her from jobless, unemployed, and single mother to one of the bestselling authors of all time. Now the article explores the view of self-realisation using the movie *Magalir Mattum*. *Magalir Mattum* is the story of the separation of three friends and how their dreams are trapped in the name of marriage life. *Magalir Mattum* (Tamil) (English: *Ladies Only*, 2017) is an Indian Tamil comedy film written and directed by the director Bamma. In the film Jyothika acts as Prabhavathi aka Prabha, Saranya acts as Subbulakshmi (Subbu), Urvashi acts as Gomatha Silkurayappan (Goms/Gomu/Komatha/Komu), Bhanupriya acts as Rani Amirthakumari Gothandaraman (Rani). A Wiki article enumerates the roles of the lead women as;

Prabhavathi aka Prabha is a feisty, independent woman who makes documentaries. She lives with her two filmmaking friends, but later moves in with her future mother-in-law Gomatha Silkurayappan aka Goms, when her son leaves for a job overseas. Goms is now a retired teacher, tutoring local kids in her home. Prabha learns that Goms misses her school friends Subbulakshmi Mangalamoorthy aka Subbu and Rani Amirthakumari Gothandaraman, with whom she has lost contact for nearly 40 years. (*Magalir Mattum* (2017 film), Wikipedia)

The story brings out the issues of discrimination faced by housewives and also shows the inequality that exists in Indian society.

The character Rani, who wishes to become a bank manager ends her life being a housewife. Subbulakshmi leads a dark life attending to her ailing mother-in-law and tolerating her drunkard husband. During the journey, Rani takes control of the car that shows an underlying suppression. Subbu, who could handle the delivery of a cow, was asked to undergo an abortion. The free choice of one's actions without any external compulsion is what real independence is. Sudhir Srinivasan, on his web page, refers as;

Of course, this isn't just true of mothers. It's true of most women who have been reduced to slaving away while their loved ones take them for granted. That's

why that haunting flashback of Subbulakshmi (Saranya), Rani (Bhanupriya), and Komatha (Urvashi in top form) serves as the backbone and the life of this film. Every time the film's getting a tad preachy, a tad dreary, a part of the flashback returns to liven things up. It's a tender, gut-wrenching reminder of the exuberance they once had, of the promises of an exciting life they once nurtured. (Sudhir Srinivasan)

Rani and Subbu receive more respect and love from their family members once they decide to be self-determined. It was essential for them to make their own decisions, irrespective of their family situations. The road trip was not a proclaimed independence to them by their family members, but it was proclaimed by themselves. Once when they chose to make decisions based on their preferences and interests, the disgusting circumstances around them changed. Rani's son realized the value of the mother and her love. Her separation makes him feel guilty for being rude in her presence. The dunked husband of Subbu changes his thoughts. The absence of his wife makes him realize the value of her.

The road trip was not only a fun-filled trip, but it was also a life-changing experience, especially for Subbu and Rani who, otherwise had to lead an unwilling life. It is not always the society or the life partner who would proclaim freedom to women. Sometimes, daring decisions would also direct them towards independence. However, Prabhavathi is the personification of a maverick, who not by her parent's compulsion or the pressure from society leads her life the way she loves. As she points out in a dialogue, the real freedom of women is not about walking alone at midnight. It is about marrying the man of her own choice and doing what she loves. Suganth for the *Times of India* writes,

It also creates an impression that it is only the earlier generation of women that faced issues of discrimination and this generation has it quite good, if you are to go by the character of Prabha, who is pretty much an independent woman. And this feels quite misleading. More than being a character, Prabha seems like a catalyst — a storytelling device. We don't really get an insight into her. "Manasukku pudichavana kalyanam pannanum, manasukku pudichavan kooda vaazhanum. Adhu dhaan real liberation," Prabha says at one point, and it feels like a rather simplistic defining of the views of this crucial character. (Suganth, TOI)

Every woman should find her voice and express her truths sincerely. Her autonomy emerges when she refuses to heed those who claim that women must remain silent about their experiences of discrimination and marginalization. She needs to create her guidelines. Women need to be courageous enough to express themselves in any manner they choose. Every person possesses a self that can either be limited or enhanced depending on their self-awareness. By fostering positive self-expression, greater independence can be attained. Building one's self-confidence allows space for showcasing their abilities. Thus, to be an independent woman, one must be an independent thinker. A thorough examination of J.K. Rowling's life and the film *Magalir Mattum* reveals that each individual holds the key to their independence. The real paths to freedom for women are self-determination, self-awareness, and self-expression. It is that women have to understand who aspires for success in their lives. Hence, the independence of a woman comes from within the individual.

Discussions

In this discussion section, one can explore how women's independence begins with the situation of inner awakening rather than external liberation from stereotypic or patriarchal domination. This analysis highlights how J.K. Rowling's personal life and the lead characters such as Prabha, Subbulakshmi, Gomatha Silkurayappan and Rani Amirthakumari in the

Tamil film *Magalir Mattum* demonstrate the transformative influence of self-realization, resilience, and self-determination in confronting social and personal challenges.

J.K. Rowling's Failure as a Catalyst for Her Independence

J.K. Rowling's life story exemplifies the profound impact of self-awareness and inner strength. Despite facing numerous challenges—including the death of her mother, a failed marriage, single motherhood, and financial hardship—Rowling found solace and purpose in writing. She has described herself as "the biggest failure," yet it was through embracing this failure that she discovered her true potential.

Rowling maintains a perfect balance between providing clues for her readers and maintaining the secret of the novels. Most readers are surprised at the end of the novels, but also wonder how they missed clues that seem obvious with hindsight. Rowling's sharp wit, humour, and imagination are unrivalled in children's literature. Rowling has said that Jane Austen is her favourite author. (Christy. A., DR. A. J. Manju, 69)

Rowling's journey underscores the concept of self-determination as a human rights approach, where individuals assert control over their lives despite external constraints. Vartika writes about J.K. Rowling in the *LinkedIn* article;

During one fine morning in 1990, when she was on a train ride from Manchester to London, she formed the entire story from an idea and started developing the story of Harry Potter on that journey. Unfortunately, her mother died later that year which halted her writing process for some time.

Her life had different plans when she moved to Portugal in 1992 to teach English as a foreign language. She met a man, married him, and had a daughter. A year later she parted ways with her then-husband and filed for a divorce in 1993.

This was the turning point of her life when she along with her infant daughter moved to Edinburgh, Scotland to be near her sister with *three chapters of Harry Potter in her suitcase.*

It was the most devastating period of Rowling's life where she was divorced, jobless, and a single mother of an infant. She suffered severe bouts of depression but she persevered. When life was dark and gloomy, she found the light at the end of a tunnel - always pushing through the trials and tribulations life would throw at her. (Vartika Ashyap)

Rowling's storytelling reflects the values of self-determination, underscoring the significance of personal agency and resilience. Her journey to success exemplifies the belief that genuine independence originates from within, fueled by self-confidence and resolve.

Exploration of Women's Liberation in *Magalir Mattum*

The film *Magalir Mattum* presents a powerful depiction of women's fight for independence in a male-dominated society. The characters Rani and Subbulakshmi embody women whose dreams are stifled by societal norms and family responsibilities. Rani, who once aspired to be a bank manager, finds herself restricted to the role of a homemaker. Subbulakshmi spends her days caring for her sick mother-in-law and enduring the mistreatment from her husband. Their enlightening journey begins with a road trip, signifying a departure from their oppressive circumstances. This journey serves as a metaphor for self-exploration and empowerment, exemplifying the notion of self-determination as a fundamental principle towards achieving independence. The film explores feminist themes, emphasizing the need for women's autonomy and the obstacles they encounter while trying to

reclaim their identities. It resonates with feminist film theory, which analyzes how women are portrayed in media and supports the notion of women's agency in storytelling.

Conclusion

J.K. Rowling's life and the three lead women characters Prabha, Subbulakshmi, Gomatha and Rani in the film *Magalir Mattum* highlight the significance of inner strength and self-determination in achieving true independence in their lives. These instances demonstrate that women's liberation is not solely reliant on external factors but is deeply rooted in personal willpower and spirit. By opening their inner selves and overcoming stereotypical social norms, women can redefine their identities and attain success in their lives.

References

- [1] Christy. A. & Dr. A. J. Manju "A Study Of J. K. Rowling Harry Potter And The Philosopher's Stone" *Iconic Research And Engineering Journals*, Volume 1 Issue 4 2017, pp. 69-71.
- [2] Joanne Rowling. *jkrowling.com*, <https://www.jkrowling.com/about/> Accessed on 15 Nov 2024.
- [3] *Magalir Mattum*. Brama (Director). Flim, 2D entertainment, 2017.
- [4] *Magalir Mattum* (2017 film), Wikipedia.
- [5] Pugh, Tison. *Harry Potter and Beyond: On J. K. Rowling's Fantasies and Other Fictions*. University of South Carolina Press, 2020. *JSTOR*, <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvs09qvw> Accessed on 15 Nov 2024.
- [6] Sudhir Srinivasan. "Magalir Mattum: A necessary, even if not a terrific." <https://sudhir-srinivasan.com/2017/09/15/magalir-mattum-a-necessary-even-if-not-a-terrific-film/> Accessed on 15 Nov 2024.
- [7] Suganth, M. "Magalir Mattum Movie Review." *Times of India*, [HTTPS://TIMESOFINDIA.INDIATIMES.COM/ENTERTAINMENT/TAMIL/MOVIE-REVIEWS/MAGALIR-MATTUM/MOVIE-REVIEW/60507803.CMS](https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/entertainment/tamil/movie-reviews/magalir-mattum/movie-review/60507803.cms) Accessed on 15 Nov 2024.
- [8] Vartika Kashyap. "Rejection. Failure. Success: The Inspirational Story of J.K Rowling." March 5, 2019. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/rejection-failure-success-inspirational-story-jk-rowling-kashyap/> Accessed on 15 Nov 2024.

Author (s) Contribution Statement: Nil

Author (s) Acknowledgement: Nil

Author (s) Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

The content of the article is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.